

Economic Rehabilitation and Stability Measures in Post-Partition Sindh, Pakistan

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Abstract

This research paper investigates the socio-economic and political landscape of Sindh (Pakistan) during the tumultuous years of 1947-1948, a critical period marked by the partition of India and the emergence of Pakistan. Focusing on the province of Sindh, the study delves into the multifaceted impact of these historical events, particularly exploring the economic crisis that unfolded in the aftermath of partition. The economic upheaval in Sindh is examined through the lens of soaring inflation, supply disruptions, and the abrupt departure of a significant Hindu population. The departure of Hindus, particularly those in administrative and business roles, created administrative challenges and a substantial deficit in the financial and human resources of the region. The paper scrutinizes the government's response to these challenges, highlighting efforts to retain the Hindu community and stabilize the local economy.

The financial strain faced by Sindh is explored in depth, analysing the deficit incurred during the fiscal year 1947-1948. The study also scrutinizes the government's policy initiatives, such as the Sind Economic Rehabilitation Ordinance, designed to address economic issues and administer control over certain sectors. Amidst the crisis, the government implemented measures to stabilize essential services and attempted to curb the departure of Hindus, who were considered vital to the functioning of the province. The research examines the imposition of travel restrictions and departure notices, which played a crucial role in shaping the movement of people during this period. By analysing historical records, government documents, and personal accounts, this research paper aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the intricate dynamics that defined Sindh's transition during this pivotal phase of South Asian history.

Keywords Sindhi-Hindu, Sindh in 1947-48, Financial Strains, Partition of India and Pakistan, Emergence of Pakistan, Post-partition, Migration, Exodus.

Introduction

The partition of India in 1947, a seminal moment in history, not only heralded the political independence of the nation but also initiated a profound transformation that reverberated across its diverse communities. Among those profoundly affected were the Sindhi-Hindu diaspora, whose lives were upended by mass migration as the subcontinent underwent a seismic shift.

Aim of study

The objective of this paper is to study Economic Rehabilitation and Stability Measures in Post-Partition Sindh, Pakistan.

Review of Literature

India's independence was formally announced by Louis, First Earl Mountbatten of Burma, the last Viceroy of India, on 3 June 1947, in New Delhi. Mountbatten, having returned from London, held crucial meetings with leaders like Jawaharlal Nehru, Muhammad Ali Jinnah, and others. On 3 June, Mountbatten's speech, along with others, was broadcasted, marking the historic announcement. Sindhi people, like the rest of India, eagerly listened, with apprehension and hope[1]. By mid-June, the Muslim League, Sikhs,

and Congress had all approved Partition. Sindh, with a Muslim League government in place, voted to become part of Pakistan on 26 June. Sindhi Muslims were excited about independence and a new social order, while Sindhi Hindus were apprehensive about their future. While communal violence was prevalent in other parts of India, Sindh remained relatively free from such incidents, with only a minor one in Jacobabad on 6 June 1947 [2]. However, the absence of violence didn't ease Sindhi Hindus' fears of potential mistreatment in a Muslim state. Hindus in Sindh, dominant in trade, education, bureaucracy, and judiciary, feared losing their power and privilege with the creation of Pakistan. The uncertainty led some to consider migration. Dr. Choithram Gidwani expressed doubts about Muslim League's intentions, questioning the reliability of assurances. In the weeks leading to Partition, many Hindus blocked lines of credit to Muslim landowners, intensifying the tension. The Sindh government faced challenges finding accommodation for the increasing number of Muslim refugees and froze essential building materials, sparking rumours of freezing all Hindu bank accounts. Despite an appearance of calm, the atmosphere was tense, and by late June, the "nervous peace" prevailed. The veneer of calm concealed the shifting dynamics between Hindus and Muslims in Sindh. The uncertainty forced some Sindhi Hindus to contemplate migration, while Muslims felt emboldened. Reports of communal violence from other parts of the country and the influx of Sindhi Hindus from Baluchistan and NWFP heightened anxiety. Some Sindhi Hindus held meetings to explore ways to protect their interests under Muslim majority rule. [3]The atmosphere of tension persisted, and migration became a topic of discussion among the community.

Main Text

Navigating Challenges and Government's Response-

By mid-October 1947, Karachi experienced a notable surge in prices, exemplified by the skyrocketing cost of imported cigarettes. The disruption of trade and communication between India and Pakistan led to a redirection of Sindh's regular supply of cigarettes to provinces like West Punjab, NWFP, and Baluchistan [4]. This resulted in shortages and contributed to the overall economic turmoil. The broader economic landscape in Sindh was marked by staggering inflation. Essential goods witnessed a swift rise in demand, far outstripping the available supply. Sindh's economy struggled under the weight of disrupted trade channels, creating a precarious situation where demand eclipsed the availability of vital commodities.

Also, the Hindu administrators (which were integral to the functioning of government offices) left in large numbers. In addition to this, attempts were made to replace them with Muhajirs and Punjabi Muslims, which created challenges due to their unfamiliarity with Sindhi language and customs [5]. Sindh's economic and financial structure, which historically relied heavily on Hindu businessmen and moneylenders, faced collapse. The departure of Hindus, who played a pivotal role in the economic ecosystem, further strained an already overstressed economic framework. The economic crisis, as described by Premier Khuhro, represented an "unprecedented difficulty" arising from the dislocation of vital trade channels, the drying up of credit sources, and the escalating burden of expenditure due to the influx of refugees.

By February 1948, Sindh found itself grappling with a substantial budgetary deficit amounting to Rs 2.57 crores for the fiscal year 1947-48 [6]. This deficit was a direct consequence of a myriad of factors, including the sudden dislocation of crucial trade channels, the drying up of credit sources, and the unforeseen burden of expenditure triggered by the massive influx of refugees into the province. As the usual economic flow, which relied on consistent trade routes and supplies, experienced a severe jolt. The consequent scarcity of goods contributed to an inflationary spiral, impacting the overall financial stability of the province. The financial strain was further heightened by the colossal burden of expenditure imposed on the province. The sudden influx of refugees placed an almost superhuman burden on Sindh's comparatively slender resources. The departure of key economic contributors, particularly the exodus of Hindus who historically played a significant role in Sindh's economic and financial sectors, contributed to the financial strain [7]. The collapse of the economic structure, dependent on Hindu businessmen and moneylenders, left a void that further amplified the deficit.

In the wake of unprecedented economic challenges faced by Sindh in the aftermath of Partition, the provincial government, under Premier Khuhro's leadership, implemented a series of responses to address the economic turmoil. This section elucidates the key measures taken by the government to stabilize the economy and alleviate the financial strain. To contend with the economic crisis, the Sindh government introduced the Sind Economic Rehabilitation Ordinance in late October 1947. This legislative move aimed to appoint a rehabilitation officer responsible for monitoring unoccupied land, buildings, and businesses. [8] The rehabilitation officer had the authority to compel the original owners to resume operations or face seizure, subsequently leasing the business to incoming

Muhajirs. This measure essentially amounted to the state's intervention in the management of businesses to mitigate economic challenges.

Given the disruption of trade and communication between India and Pakistan, essential goods faced a severe supply-demand imbalance, leading to staggering inflation. To mitigate this, the government implemented regulations on various goods, including bullion, jewellery, cloth, soap, surgical and optical goods, food grains, building materials, and machinery. These measures aimed to stabilize prices and ensure the availability of essential items. Premier Khuhro's government recognized the fiscal strain on Sindh's economy and acknowledged the impending deficit. The government engaged in financial planning to manage this deficit, exploring strategies to balance revenues and expenditures in the wake of economic challenges.

Recognizing the departure of Hindu merchants and bureaucrats as a significant blow to the economy, the Sindh government-initiated efforts to retain this crucial demographic. Senior government officials, including Premier Khuhro, personally visited Hindus in Karachi, assuring them of their security and inviting those who had left to return. In response to critical voices from the Hindu press, the government took measures to control the narrative [9]. The publication of *Hindustan* and *Sansar Samachar* was banned for two months at the end of October 1947. Pre-censorship was imposed on the *Sind Observer*, and warnings were issued to the Hindu press against publishing content deemed disloyal to Pakistan. This crackdown aimed to manage public perception and prevent the exacerbation of existing tensions. The clampdown on Hindu press and the ban on certain publications were additional measures to control information flow and maintain stability.

The mass exodus of Hindus from Sindh in the aftermath of Partition also presented unprecedented administrative challenges to the provincial government led by Premier Khuhro. This section explores the circumstances leading to the exodus, the administrative complexities faced by the government, and the measures taken to address the migration of a significant population. Communal tensions, fuelled by the broader context of Partition-related violence in other regions of India, contributed to a sense of insecurity among Sindhi Hindus. Reports of violence, coupled with the fear of potential repercussions in a Muslim-majority state, prompted many Hindus to contemplate migration. Acts of intimidation, such as the refusal of some Sindhi Muslim workers to serve Hindu landowners, added to the apprehensions of the Hindu community. The economic landscape played a crucial role in the exodus, with many affluent Sindhi Hindus perceiving a loss of power, privilege, and status in the new socio-political order. The freezing of essential building materials and rumours of freezing private bank accounts further escalated concerns. This legislative measure aimed to monitor and regulate unoccupied land, buildings, and businesses, attempting to stabilize the economy amidst the departure of Hindu merchants and administrators. The government's efforts were driven by the need to prevent a collapse of the economic and financial structure. [10]

The government's contemplation of placing a ban on the exodus of non-Muslims, framed as a measure for their safety and the maintenance of peace, added to the complexity of the situation. This consideration raised concerns among the Hindu community about potential restrictions on their mobility. The departure of a significant number of Hindu bureaucrats and professionals, who had been the backbone of the administration, resulted in administrative paralysis. Government offices, courts, banks, and businesses experienced a depletion of experienced personnel. Efforts to replace Hindu employees with Muhajirs and Punjabi Muslims, while necessary, presented a challenge as the new workforce was unfamiliar with the local language and dynamics. The period following Partition witnessed a mass exodus of Hindus from Sindh, prompted by communal tensions and economic uncertainties. [11]

Premier Khuhro's government, recognizing the significance of retaining the Hindu population, undertook various efforts to reassure and placate the community. This section explores the initiatives and policies implemented by the Sindh government to retain Hindus during a tumultuous time. In a proactive move, Premier Khuhro established the Peace Board, comprising prominent Muslims and Hindus in Karachi. This board played a pivotal role in reassuring Hindus about their security and acted as a platform for hearing and addressing their grievances. The inclusive nature of this initiative aimed to foster communal harmony. Senior members of both the Sindh and Central Government including Governor Hidayatullah and Premier Khuhro, personally visited Hindu communities in Karachi. These visits were not merely symbolic but were aimed at assuring Hindus of their safety and security in Sindh. Public statements were made, inviting Sindhi Hindus who had left Pakistan to return to their home province [12]. These efforts were part of a broader strategy to prevent further migration and reassure those who had already left.

Ensuring Communal Harmony:

Extra police pickets and security arrangements were put in place to ensure the safety of Hindu celebrations. This aimed to create an environment where diverse religious practices could coexist harmoniously. While there were instances of crackdowns on certain publications, the government also engaged in dialogue with the Hindu press. Premier Khuhro issued warnings to the press, urging them to refrain from content that could be perceived as disloyalty to Pakistan. This attempt at communication aimed to prevent the exacerbation of tensions and maintain a semblance of impartiality [13]. The government's efforts to retain Hindus in Sindh during the challenging post-Partition period reflected a multi-faceted approach. From creating platforms for communal dialogue to enacting economic rehabilitation measures, these initiatives sought to reassure the Hindu community and emphasize their integral role in the province. Premier Khuhro's government undertook various measures to address these economic hardships and stabilize the financial structure of the province. [14]

Initiatives such as the Peace Board and public assurances by senior government officials were designed to reassure Hindus of their security and encourage their continued participation in the economic life of the province. Recognizing the importance of the business community in stabilizing the economy, Premier Khuhro and other government officials engaged in outreach efforts. These initiatives included visits to business establishments, dialogues with business leaders, and attempts to address their concerns. The goal was to foster collaboration between the government and the business community to navigate the economic challenges. To ensure the continuity of economic activities, the government implemented security measures during critical times, such as religious festivals. Extra police pickets and security arrangements were put in place to safeguard economic functions and prevent disruptions [15]. This approach aimed to create an environment conducive to economic stability. The measures implemented by the Sindh government against economic challenges reflected a comprehensive strategy to address the multifaceted issues arising from the aftermath of Partition. From regulatory frameworks to initiatives promoting economic continuity and stability, these measures were crucial in navigating the economic turmoil of the time. In the tumultuous aftermath of Partition, Sindh witnessed significant demographic shifts and communal tensions. The government, led by Premier Khuhro, responded to the challenges by imposing travel restrictions and instituting departure notices. This section explores the context, implementation, and consequences of these measures, shedding light on the complex dynamics of population movement during this period. As communal violence erupted in various parts of India during the partition, concerns about the safety of minority communities, particularly Hindus, became a prevailing issue. In this atmosphere of fear and distrust, the Sindh government, like others in the newly formed Pakistan, grappled with the task of maintaining order and safeguarding its citizens. This move was motivated by a desire to prevent large-scale migrations, which could exacerbate an already volatile situation. The restriction aimed to maintain stability, protect citizens, and avoid inter-communal conflicts. To regulate the exodus of non-Muslims, especially Hindus, the Sindh government introduced a system of departure notices. Individuals wishing to leave the province were required to provide a two weeks' notice to the government. This measure was intended to streamline the movement of people, manage the flow of refugees, and ensure a semblance of order during a critical period. Premier Khuhro's statement about considering a "ban on the exodus of non-Muslims from Sindh" created apprehension among Hindus. While the government suggested this measure to guarantee the safety of non-Muslims, it also fuelled fears that departure might be prohibited entirely. The announcement contributed to a climate of uncertainty, prompting discussions about the potential impact on migration patterns.

Indeed, Sindh's "partition" in 1947 was a deterritorialized and demographic partition, producing approximately a million non-Muslim refugees (not all of them Sindhi-speaking) [16].

Conclusion

The research findings on post-Partition Sindh offer valuable insights into the multifaceted challenges faced by the region during a tumultuous period in South Asian history. The significance of these findings can be understood through several key dimensions:

1. Economic Turmoil and Financial Strain.
2. Government Response and Administrative Challenges.
3. Exodus of Hindus and Government Efforts to Retain.
4. Measures Against Economic Challenges.
5. Travel Restrictions and Departure Notices.

6. Overall Impact and Broader Implications.

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